

DESIGN OF NOVEL MULTI-PHASE COMPOSITE SCAFFOLDS FOR BONE REGENERATION

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SUMMARY

The design of bioactive scaffolds able to guide cellular processes involved in tissue-genesis is key determinant for bone tissue engineering. The aim of this study was the design of novel biomaterials able to: i) promote the osteogenic differentiation of human mesenchymal stem cells and ii) be further processed into well controlled 3D porous scaffolds.

Keywords: Bone regeneration; Composite scaffold; Gas foaming; Poly(ϵ -caprolactone); Zein.

INTRODUCTION

The repair and reconstruction of bone skeletal defects by the traditional medical treatments, like autologous or allogenic bone graft, is often impaired by the complexity of the procedures involved as well as due to donor site scarcity, foreign body reaction and pathogen transfer occurrences [1-5]. Recently, Tissue Engineering (TE) has emerged as an alternative and very promising approach aiming at the regeneration of biological tissues, including bone and cartilage [6]. To achieve this aim, TE strategies combine material, cells and molecular cues with the ultimate goal to promote and guide the repair and regeneration of the damaged biological tissue. Therefore, for the success of any TE strategy, great importance is related to the optimal selection of materials and cells, as well as the possibility of a fine control of the micro-structural properties of biocompatible and biodegradable materials/scaffolds.

The use of human mesenchymal stem cells (hMSC) in tissue engineering and regenerative medicine has steadily increased over the past years. Indeed, hMSCs have the ability to differentiate into multiple cell-type and have the great potential of expansion and lineage-specific differentiation when combined with autologous sources [7,8]. Additionally, the hMSCs may enhance the process of bone tissue regeneration when encased in tissue-specific scaffolds and implanted into different tissue sites [8].

A large number of biodegradable material scaffolds, in particular ceramics and polymers of natural or synthetic origins, have been investigated for bone repair and regeneration [3]. Indeed, all these materials may be specifically selected/selected in order to optimize the final properties of the new-engineered tissue. For instance, ceramics characterized by a well definite porous structure and degradability have been

prepared as porous scaffolds for bone repair [9]. Furthermore, when incorporated into a thermoplastic polymeric matrix as inorganic filler, these materials may improve its bone regeneration ability *in vitro* and/or *in vivo* [10].

Blending synthetic and natural polymers is another successful approach to control the physical properties, mainly hydrophilicity and degradability, of a polymeric scaffolds. Indeed, when incorporated into a synthetic polymeric matrix, natural materials may allow a better control over its degradability and may also enhance cell seeding, proliferation and differentiation [11,12]. Among the natural polymeric materials, zein, a major storage protein of corn, has been investigated for bone TE applications [13,14]. In particular, zein scaffolds showed excellent bone regeneration capabilities, being able to promote MSCs adhesion, proliferation and osteogenic differentiation [14].

We recently reported the thermoplasticization process of zein with the aim of prepare a thermoplastic material suitable to be melt processed into 3D porous structures with the technologies commonly used for the synthetic polymers, such as gas foaming [15].

In this work we prepared multi-phase composites made of poly(ϵ -caprolactone) (PCL), thermoplastic zein (TZ) and hydroxyapatite (HA) for bone regeneration. The micro-structural properties of these systems have been evaluated and compared to those of the pure PCL and PCL-HA. hMSCs were seeded onto the biomaterials to evaluate their capacity to adhere to the matrix, proliferate and differentiate into osteoblast. Finally, by starting from the multi-phase systems prepared, we designed 3D porous scaffolds by the gas foaming technology. In particular, a detailed investigation about the gas foaming process of the three-phase system with different HA loading has been performed in order to design porous scaffold that meet the micro-structural requirements for bone regeneration.

EXPERIMENTAL

PCL (MW = 65kDa, $T_m = 59-64^\circ\text{C}$, $T_g = -60^\circ\text{C}$, and $\rho = 1.145\text{g/cm}^3$) and maize zein powder (cod.: Z3625, batch: 065K0110) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Italy). Poly(ethylene glycol) (PEG) 400 was purchased by Fluka (Italy) and used as plasticizer for the preparation of the TZ. HA granules (ENGIpore, batch 071105, 70-100 μm and 250-355 μm particles size ranges) were purchased by Finceramica (Faenza, Italy). The TZ was prepared as described in a previously reported work by using an internal mixer (Rheomix 600 Haake, Germany) [15]. The PCL, TZ and HA components selected for the preparation of the three-phase systems have been melt-mixed by using the composition reported in Table 1.

Scaffold formulations	PCL [wt%]	TZ [wt%]	HA [wt%]
PCL	100	-	-
PCL-HA	80	-	20
PCL/TZ	60	40	-
PCL/TZ-HA	48	32	20

Table 1. Formulation of the different biomaterials.

Materials characterization

TGA was performed to evaluate the thermal stability of the different systems prepared by using a TGA 2950 (TA Instruments, USA) and performing the analysis over a temperature range of 30 $^\circ\text{C}$ to 600 $^\circ\text{C}$ at 10 $^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ under inert atmosphere.

A DMA Triton 2000 (Triton technology, Ltd. UK) was used in order to characterize the dynamic-mechanical properties of the different PCL-based systems. Rectangular samples ($l = 8\text{mm}$, $W = 27\text{mm}$ and $t = 1\text{mm}$) were tested in a dual cantilever bending mode, at an oscillatory frequency of 1Hz and in the $-130^{\circ}\text{C} \div 50^{\circ}\text{C}$ temperature range ($2^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ heating rate).

Tensile tests were performed at room temperature according to ASTM standard D1708-02 by using a 4204 Universal Testing Machine (Instron, USA) with 1kN load cell to evaluate Yielding stress (σ_Y), stress at break (σ_B) and elongation at break (ϵ_B). Five samples for each composition were tested.

The hydrophilicity of the biomaterials prepared was evaluated by contact angle and water absorption measurements. The contact angle measurements were performed on a Contact angle System OCA20 (Dataphysics, Italy) by pouring $1\mu\text{L}$ water droplet on the surface of the scaffold and measuring the contact angle by Software SCA20 (Dataphysics, Italy). Ten measurements on different regions of the surface for each composition were performed. For the water absorption measurements, three disc-shaped samples (10mm in diameter and 1mm thick) were soaked in dH_2O at 37°C and the degree of swelling measured at different time up to 60 days. At selected immersion time, the materials were dried and the micro-architecture evaluated by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). For SEM analysis, the samples were cross-sectioned, gold sputtered and analyzed by SEM LEICA S440 at an accelerating voltage of 20 kV, at various magnifications.

The biological response of the different scaffolds prepared was investigated by using bone marrow derived human mesenchymal stem cells (hMSCs). hMSCs at the 7th passage, were cultured in α -Modified Eagle's medium (α -MEM) (Bio Wittaker, Belgium) containing 10% (v/v) FBS, 100 U ml^{-1} penicillin and 0.1 mg ml^{-1} streptomycin (HyClone, UK), in a humidified atmosphere at 37°C and 5% CO_2 . Scaffolds for cell-culture experiments ($d = 10\text{ mm}$ and $h = 1\text{ mm}$) were γ -sterilized before seeding. 4×10^5 cells/scaffold, resuspended in $50\mu\text{l}$ of medium, were statically seeded onto the scaffold and the cell/scaffold constructs were maintained in culture for 21 days and the cell-culture medium was changed every 3–4 days. Cell proliferation was evaluated by using Cell proliferation was determined by DNA analysis. At predetermined time point, three replicate scaffolds were washed with phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) (Euroclone, Wetherby, UK) and transferred to centrifuge tubes containing 1 mL deionised molecular-grade pure water. The tube were then transferred and stored at -20°C . After thawing, the samples were treated ultrasonically in an ice-water bath for 10min and the released amount of DNA was measured from supernatant. Total amount of DNA was detected using Hoechst 33258 dye (DNA quantification kit, Sigma-Aldrich, Italy). Sample fluorescence was measured with a luminescent spectrometer (LS50B, Perkin-Elmer, Waltham, USA) at an excitation and emission wavelengths of 360nm and 460nm, respectively. Samples were compared to the standard curve to determine DNA content per composite. hMSCs morphology and proliferation were additionally investigated by SEM and histology. hMSCs osteogenic differentiation was evaluated by ALP. The cell/scaffold constructs were homogenized in $800\mu\text{L}$ 0.1% Triton-X100 + 0.01% NaCl followed by sonication for 6min. ALP activity was measured using a biochemical assay (Sigma-Aldrich, Italy) based on conversion of p-nitrophenyl phosphatase to p-nitrophenol which was measured spectrophotometrically at 405nm. ALP activity is expressed as micromoles of p-nitrophenol released. Scaffolds without cells served as control groups.

Porous scaffold preparation

For the preparation of porous scaffolds starting from the different systems prepared, we used the gas foaming technology [16]. Disc-shaped samples ($d = 10\text{mm}$, $h = 2\text{mm}$) were saturated with CO_2 in a high-pressure vessel (HiP, Pennsylvania, USA), at a saturation pressure (P_{sat}) of 140 bar and at a saturation temperature (T_{sat}) of 70°C for 4 hours. After the blowing agent solubilization, the samples were cooled or heated to the desired foaming temperature (T_{F}) with a precise cooling profile. The pressure was then quenched to ambient pressure with controlled pressure drop rates.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In Figure 1 are reported the results of the TGA/DTGA analysis performed on the different systems prepared.

Figure 1 – (A) TGA and (B) DTGA curves of the different biomaterials prepared.

When mixed with the TZ, the thermal stability of the PCL-based biomaterials decreased, as evidenced by the decomposition peaks in the $200\text{--}350^\circ\text{C}$ observed for the PCL/TZ and PCL/TZ-HA systems. Additionally, these systems evidenced a first peak at

100°C that may be attributed to the evaporation of the water and/or plasticizer into the TZ phase. The third peak at 410°C ca. can be attributed to the thermal degradation of the PCL. The addition of the HA produced an additional weight loss at 350°C ca. (see Figure 1B) and the presence of a residual weight at 600°C of about 20wt-% for the PCL-HA, equal to the concentration of the inorganic filler into the polymeric matrix (see Figure 1A). Furthermore, the TZ does not degrade completely at the final test temperature [15], as observed in the case of PCL/TZ thermogram, where a residue of 4wt-% ca. at 600°C was present (Figure 1A). PCL/TZ-HA blend, for the same reason, had a final residue at 600°C of 24%.

The formation of heterogeneous systems, as a consequence of the immiscibility of the PCL and TZ, was confirmed by the results of the DMA analysis (data not showed). Indeed, differently from the PCL and PCL-HA systems, the PCL/TZ and PCL/TZ-HA were characterized by two different peaks in the $\tan \delta$ curves, at -60°C and 40°C ca. These peaks indicated the presence of the two glass transition temperatures of PCL and TZ, respectively and, demonstrated that, after blending, the two polymers formed a multi-phase system [17].

In Figure 2 are reported the results of the tensile characterization of the different biomaterials prepared. The higher values of the stress were obtained for the neat PCL. Indeed, both the HA and the TZ decreased the values of σ_Y and σ_B . In particular, the addition of the TZ significantly increased the stiffness of the material, as evidenced by the increase of the stress values into the initial linear portion of the stress vs. strain curves (data not shown) and by the decrease of the σ_B of two orders of magnitude. Similar trend was observed when the HA was added into both PCL and PCL/TZ systems.

Figure 2 – Tensile properties of the different biomaterials prepared.

Parameters such as surface topography, wettability and charge strongly influence MSCs adhesion, proliferation and differentiation [18-21]. Furthermore, the enhancement of the wettability of a polymer scaffold was found to be very important for an homogeneous and sufficient cell seeding in three dimensions [18].

The results of the contact angle and water absorption measurements, reported in Figures 3 and 4, respectively, showed a clear relationship with biomaterial formulations, with TZ incorporation as a possible way to enhance the hydrophilicity of PCL scaffolds.

Indeed, with respect to pure PCL, the addition of TZ produced an enhancement of the wettability of the system, as evidenced by the decrease of the contact angle from 82.5 to 72.5°. However, the contact angle measurement was strongly affected by the topological characteristic of the surfaces of the sample. Indeed, the contact angle values of the PCL-HA and PCL/TZ-HA composites were comparable with those obtained for the systems prepared without HA, because of the enhanced roughness of the test sample surface (data not reported).

Figure 3 – Contact angle measurements of A) PCL and B) PCL/TZ.

The enhanced hydrophilic properties of the PCL/TZ based systems are also consistent with the water absorption measurements reported in Figure 4. Indeed, the weight of PCL and PCL-HA remained almost unchanged during the immersion period, while significant changes may be observed for the PCL/TZ and PCL/TZ-HA systems. In particular, the PCL/TZ and PCL/TZ-HA showed a rapid initial water absorption, followed by the progressive weight decrease, as a consequence of the swelling and degradation of the TZ phase.

These results are consistent with those of the SEM analysis reported in Figure 5, that showed the morphology of the PCL/TZ and PCL/TZ-HA at different soaking time. The composition of the blends, close to the phase inversion point (see Table 1) [16,17], allowed the formation of co-continuous micro-structures and, therefore, the constant exposure of the two different components to water. As a direct consequence, 19 and 45 days of soaking in water produced the formation of porosity on the surfaces (Figures 5C and D) and into the bulk (Figures 5E and F) of the PCL/TZ and PCL/TZ-HA, respectively, with respect to the initial blend morphologies (see Figures 5A and B), due to the faster degradation of the TZ with respect to the PCL. Therefore, these systems may assure the initial mechanical properties of the bulk material, while the progressive increase of porosity during the degradation process of the TZ (see Figure 5) may create additional surface for cell adhesion and colonization.

Figure 4 – Effect of biomaterial formulation on weight evolution (m_t) during water absorption measurements at 37°C, with respect to the initial weight (m_0).

Figure 5 – SEM micrographs of A) PCL/TZ and B) PCL/TZ-HA surfaces; SEM micrographs of the C) and D) surfaces and E) and G) cross-sections of PCL/TZ at 19 days of soaking in water at 37°C and PCL/TZ-HA at 45 days of soaking, respectively.

In order to assess the ability of the designed biomaterials to be used for bone tissue engineering applications, a preliminary cell/scaffold interaction study has been performed *in vitro*, by using hMSCs. The results of this study (not shown) evidenced

improved hMSCs adhesion and proliferation when seeded onto the PCL/TZ-HA biomaterials, if compared to the other systems prepared. This effect may be ascribed to the different composition/architecture of this system, if compared to the PCL and PCL-HA. Indeed, a large number of studies proved the ability of zein scaffolds to support MSCs adhesion and proliferation [13]. Furthermore, when blended with PCL, the TZ may improve the hydrophilic properties of the scaffolds (Figures 3 and 4) and the adsorption of the serum-derived ECM proteins responsible of the adhesion and proliferation of cells [19].

In designing novel biomaterials for bone tissue engineering, one of the most important aspect is related to the possibility of preparing porous scaffolds with well controlled micro-structural properties. Indeed, several studies have been recently reported about the key role of the porosity and pore size distributions on the adhesion of cells, as well as their growth, proliferation, differentiation and biosynthesis [22-24]. The multi-phase systems prepared have been therefore further processed by the gas foaming technology in order to design porous scaffolds with open pore porosity. In Figure 6 are reported the microscope images of PCL/TZ system before and after the gas foaming process (Figure A) and the SEM micrographs of the cross-sections of the foamed scaffolds (Figures B-D).

Figure 6 – (A) Optical images of PCL/TZ before and after the gas foaming step; SEM micrographs of the porous scaffolds with (B) 0%, (C) 10% and (D) 20% of HA.

The visual observation of the foamed blend evidenced significant changes after foaming, while the sample maintained its disc-shaped geometry (Figure 6A). However, with respect to the unfoamed blend (Figures 5A and B), the porous scaffolds were

characterized by a highly interconnected porosity (see SEM micrographs of Figures 6B-D). These results evidenced the feasibility of the multi-phase biomaterials prepared to be processed in order to design porous scaffolds for bone tissue engineering applications.

CONCLUSIONS

In this paper we prepared novel multi-phase biomaterials for bone tissue engineering.

The biomaterials have been prepared by mixing PCL, TZ and HA as osteoconductive inorganic filler. The optimization of material composition and mixing procedure allowed the control over the micro-structural and hydrophilic properties of the systems. Furthermore, the results of the cell-scaffold interaction study suggested a key role of biomaterial formulation on hMSCs adhesion, proliferation and osteogenic differentiation.

Finally, by using the gas foaming technology we demonstrated the possibility of preparing porous scaffolds with well controlled interconnected porosity and pore size distributions, starting from the multi-phase systems prepared.

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